

**NILRADIKALI BERILGAN BA'ZI YECHILUVCHAN LEYBNITS ALGEBRALARINING
1/2-DIFFERENSIALLASHLARI**

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada nilradikali maksimal uzunlikdagi kvazi-filiform Leybnits algebrasi bo'lgan yechiluvchan Leybnits algebrasining 1/2-differensiallashlari o'rganilgan.

Kalit soz'lar: Leybnits algebrasi, yechiluvchan Leybnits algebrasi, nilradikal, algebraning 1/2-differensiallashi.

Abstract: In this article we study 1/2-derivations of solvable Leibniz algebras whose nilradical is a quasi-filiform Leibniz algebra of maximal length.

Keywords: Leibniz algebra, solvable Leibniz algebra, nilradical, 1/2-derivation of algebra

Аннотация: В данной работе изучаются 1/2-дифференцирования разрешимых алгебр Лейбница, нильрадикал которых является квази-филиформной алгеброй Лейбница максимальной длины.

Ключевые слова: алгебра Лейбница, разрешимая алгебра Лейбница, нильрадикал, 1/2-дифференцирование алгебры.

Ta'rif 1. F maydon ustida aniqlangan L algebraning ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlari uchun quyidagi Leybnits ayniyati bajarilsa,

$$[x, [y, z]] = [[x, y], z] - [[x, z], y],$$

L algebra Leybnits algebrasi deyiladi, bu yerda $[-, -]$ – L da aniqlangan ko'paytirish amali.

Ixtiyoriy L Leybnits algebrasi uchun quyidagi quyi markaziy va hosilaviy ketma-ketliklarni mos ravishda aniqlaymiz:

$$L^1 = L, \quad L^{k+1} = [L^k, L^1]; \quad L^{[1]} = L, \quad L^{[k+1]} = [L^{[k]}, L^{[k]}], \quad k \geq 1.$$

Ta'rif 3. L Leybnits algebrasi uchun shunday $s \in \mathbb{N}$ son mavjud bo'lib, $L^{[s]} = 0$ (mos ravishda, $L^s = 0$) bo'lsa, u holda L yechiluvchan (mos ravishda, nilpotent) Leybnits algebrasi deyiladi.

Ta'rif 4. Ixtiyoriy Leybnits algebrasining maksimal nilpotent ideali uning nilradikali deyiladi.

Ta'rif 5. L Leybnits algebra, agar $L^{n-2} \neq 0$ va $L^{n-1} = 0$ bo'lsa kvazi-filiform deyiladi, bu yerda $n = \dim L$.

Nilradikali N va to'ldiruvchi fazosining o'lchami s ga teng bo'lgan barcha yechiluvchan Leybnits algebra lari oilasini $R(N, s)$ bilan belgilaymiz.

Quyidagi teoremda nilradikali maksimal uzunlikdagi kvazi-filiform Leybnits algebra si bo'lgan va Q to'ldiruvchi fazosining o'lchami ikkiga teng bo'lgan yechiluvchan Leybnits algebra larini tasnifi keltiriladi.

Teorema 1. [2] $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebra lar oilasining ixtiyoriy algebra si quyidagi algebra ga izomorf:

$$R(M^{1,0}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_1, e_1] = e_n, & [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 2 \leq i \leq n-2, \\ [e_1, x_1] = e_1, & [e_i, x_1] = (i-2)e_i, & 3 \leq i \leq n-1, \\ [e_n, x_1] = 2e_n, & [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, \\ [e_i, x_2] = e_i, & & 2 \leq i \leq n-1. \end{cases}$$

Teorema 2. [2] $R(M^{2,\lambda}, 2)$ algebra lar oilasining ixtiyoriy algebra si quyidagi algebra lardan biriga izomorf;

$$R(M^{2,0}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 1 \leq i \leq n-3, & [e_{n-1}, e_1] = e_n, \\ [e_i, x_1] = ie_i, & 1 \leq i \leq n-2, & [e_n, x_1] = e_n, \\ [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, & [e_{n-1}, x_2] = e_{n-1}, & [e_n, x_2] = e_n. \end{cases}$$

$$R(M^{2,-1}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 1 \leq i \leq n-3, & [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, \\ [e_{n-1}, e_1] = -[e_1, e_{n-1}] = e_n, & [e_n, x_1] = -[x_1, e_n] = e_n, \\ [e_i, x_1] = ie_i, & 1 \leq i \leq n-2, \\ [e_{n-1}, x_2] = -[x_2, e_{n-1}] = e_{n-1}, & [e_n, x_2] = -[x_2, e_n] = e_n. \end{cases}$$

Ta'rif 4. Aytaylik d - L Leybnits algebra sining chiziqli almashtirishi bo'lsin. Agar ixtiyoriy $x, y \in L$ lar uchun quyidagi tenglik bajrilsa

$$d([x, y]) = \frac{1}{2} ([d(x), y] + [x, d(y)]),$$

u holda d chiziqli almashtirishga L Leybnits algebrasining $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi deyiladi.

[1] ishda $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$, $R(M^{2,0}, 2)$ va $R(M^{2,-1}, 2)$ algebralarning differensiallashlari topilgan.

Quyidagi tasdiqda $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebrani $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi topilgan.

Tasdiq 1. $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_i) = a_{1,1}x_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2.$$

Tasdiq 2. $R(M^{2,0}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda

bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_i) = a_{1,1}x_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2.$$

$R(M^{2,-1}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_1) = b_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,1}x_1,$$

$$d(x_2) = b_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,1}x_2.$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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